

Overview of Work Readiness in Industrial Practice Students

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this research is to determine the picture of work readiness of students who practice in industry. The method in this research is a literature study with descriptive methods. The journals used in this research consisted of 7 journals with similar research themes, namely student work readiness and industrial practice. The results obtained in this research are that students are more ready to work after carrying out industrial practice because students gain experience to develop skills according to their field of expertise, and students are better able to adapt to new environments. The implication of this research is to provide knowledge regarding the description of work readiness for students who practice in industry.

INTRODUCTION

Industrial work practice is a work training model that is carried out directly in the world of work to apply the competencies obtained at school and to learn competencies that have not been obtained at school due to limited tools, as well as to gain work experience in accordance with the competencies mastered by vocational school students. Djojonegoro (1998) also stated that industrial work practices are organized by vocational skills education which systematically and synchronously combines educational programs in schools and skills mastery programs obtained through working directly in the business world or industrial world (DU/DI), in a directed manner to achieve a level of professional expertise. Meanwhile, the Vocational School Curriculum (Dikmenjur, 2008) states that Industrial Work Practices are a pattern of organizing training that is managed jointly between Vocational Schools and industry/professional associations as partner institutions (IP), starting from the planning, implementation to evaluation and certification stages which constitute one program. by using various alternative forms of implementation, such as day releases, block releases, and so on. The aim of industrial work practices based on industrial work guidelines (Prasetyani, 2013) is to provide real work experience so that participants master standardized productive skill competencies, internalize industrial values and cultural attitudes that are oriented towards quality standards and an entrepreneurial spirit and form a critical, productive and work ethic. competitive. Oemar Hamalik (Hamalik, 1990) also stated that industrial practice or in some schools what is called On The Job Training (OJT) is training capital that is held in the field, aimed at providing the skills needed for a particular job in accordance with the job's ability demands. It is hoped that the implementation of industrial work practices in schools will be able to provide work experience for students to produce skilled graduates according to their field of expertise. This is done on the grounds that a professional secondary workforce is very necessary to support the growth of industrialization and the economic growth of a country. Because the more skilled and productive citizens of a nation, the stronger the country's economic capacity.

However, in reality, the low quality of education is an educational problem in Indonesia. Vocational High Schools (SMK) in preparing graduates who have abilities, skills and expertise are not yet fully ready to work so that many graduates are still unemployed. Meanwhile, the small number of job vacancies, the low quality and productivity of Human Resources (HR) is a problem in the employment sector which results in large numbers of unemployed. Willingness to work itself is defined by Fitriyanto (2006) as the overall condition of an individual which includes physical, mental and experience maturity as well as the willingness and ability to carry out a job or activity required in each job, both for people who are working and those who are not yet working, so that they are able to complete the work according to the provisions. Willingness to work is important to research because humans have the desire to live, to fulfill daily needs humans need work (Sugiarto, 2015), and to get a job work readiness is needed.

Kardimin in Maikaningrum (2016) stated that there are two factors that influence work readiness, including internal factors (both physical and mental maturity, intelligence, independence, pressure, creativity, interest, talent, mastery of knowledge and motivation). Furthermore, external factors include the role of the community, family, information about the world of work, school facilities and infrastructure, and work experience. Thus, this research wants to find out a picture of the work readiness of students who take part in work practice programs in industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Readiness refers to the assumption that an organism's satisfaction comes from the utilization of conduction units, where these units give rise to tendencies that encourage an organism to do or not do something (Yudhawati and Haryanto, 2011). According to the psychology dictionary (Chaplin, 2000), work readiness contains two meanings, namely: (a) a state of being ready to react or respond, (b) the level of development of maturity or maturity that is profitable for practicing something.

Gulo (Rosita, 2009) states that readiness is a point of maturity to be able to accept and pay attention to certain actions. The level of readiness for something is influenced by three factors, namely (a) the level of maturity which is a developmental process in which the physical and mental levels have reached perfect development in the sense of being ready to use. This maturity level is usually influenced by age and physical factors. (b) harmonious mental and emotional states, and (c) (2) past experiences, namely certain experiences obtained related to the environment, available opportunities and intentional external influences (education and teaching), as well as unintentional influences. intentional. Work willingness as defined by Hersey and Blanchard Refers to the degree to which people have the ability and willingness to complete certain tasks (Robbins, 2007).

The work readiness program is a competency based program that utilizes learning experiences to be given to students so they can work well. This program must be carried out by all parties involved in the field of education 53 The Role of Work Interests Journal of Communication Media Education Technology and Vocational Education so that the main goal can be realized (Arfandi, 2013; Asrib & Arfandi, n.d.). The characteristics of students who have work readiness according to Pujianti and Arief (Pujianto & Arief, 2017) are students who have considerations; a) have logical and objective considerations; b) have the ability and willingness to work together with other people; c) able to control oneself or emotions; d) have a critical attitude; e) have the courage to accept individual responsibility; f) have the ability to adapt to the environment and technological developments; g) and have the ambition to progress and try to keep up with developments in the field of expertise.

METHODOLOGY

The method used is literature study. The process is carried out by looking for published articles in journals and books related to the theme of work attitudes and industrial work practices. There are 7 journals which are international journals taken from several databases such as ScienceDirect, Taylor & Francis, Springer. The author searches directly from the website or also uses the help of Google Scholar and Research Gate. The process itself goes through three processes, namely: editing, organizing, and discovery. Sarah Adilah Wandansari, Hernawati (2021) explains that at the editing stage, researchers check the data obtained, especially its completeness, clarity of meaning, and harmony between one meaning and another. Next, the researcher organizes the data obtained according to the required framework. Then, the researcher carried out further analysis of the results of organizing data on learning success or academic success using established rules, theories and methods so that conclusions were found which were the results of this research. The final stage is that the researcher analyzes the data to draw a conclusion.

RESEARCH RESULT

Steps to test your results here

In this section, you should describe each step taken to complete your research. You should not include too many descriptive statistical results here; on the other hand, it should be summarized in a more readable table or graph. You should never forget the numbers for each table and chart presented in your paper.

Based on the results of a review of 7 journals related to work readiness and industrial practices, the following results were obtained:

Table 1. Results of a review of 7 journals related to work readiness and industrial practices

No	Name	Title Subject	Method	Results and Conclusions
1	Lidya Dau, Munawar Thoharudin, Dessy Triana Relita	The Influence of Industrial Work Practices on the Work Readiness of Class XII Students at Kartini Sintang Vocational School	The method used is quantitative and the form of research used is explanatory survey.	Based on the research results, it can be concluded that there is a significant influence between industrial work practices on the work readiness of class XII students at Kartini Sintang Vocational School for the 2017/2018 academic year.
2	Juliasti	The Influence of	The population is all	The results of this study

		Industrial Work Practices and Accounting Learning Achievements on the Work Readiness of Class XII Students majoring in Accounting at SMK Negeri 1 Makassar	students in class XII accounting at SMK Negeri 1 Makassar, consisting of 133 students. The sampling technique used proportionate stratified random sampling technique with a sample of 57 students. The data collection techniques used were questionnaires and documentation. The data analysis techniques used are descriptive percentage analysis, instrument testing, classical assumption testing and hypothesis testing	indicate that industrial work practices and student accounting learning achievement simultaneously have a significant effect on work readiness at a significant level
3	Aulia Nur Syaila	The Influence of Industrial Work Practices and Work Motivation on the Work Readiness of Class XII Students	The research consists of three variables, the dependent variable is industrial work practices and work motivation, and the independent variable is work readiness. Data collection was carried out using scales of industrial work practices, work motivation and work readiness. The sample in this research was 104 grade 12 students at SMK Negeri 2 Tenggara. The data analysis technique used is multiple regression test analysis.	Based on the results of the research that has been carried out, it can be concluded as follows: 1. There is an influence between industrial work practices and work motivation on the work readiness of class XII students at SMK Negeri 2 Tenggara 2. There is an influence between industrial work practices on the work readiness of class Tenggara 3. There is an influence between work motivation on the work readiness of class XII students at SMK Negeri 2 Tenggara

4	Rizal Eko Wibowo, Jarot Tri Bowo Santoso	Pengaruh Praktik Kerja Industri, Prestasi Belajar dan Motivasi Memasuki Dunia Kerja Terhadap Kesiapan Kerja Siswa Kelas XI SMK	<p>The population in this study were class XI students at SMK Palebon Semarang. The total population of the study was 283 students and the sample was 166 students</p> <p>Which is calculated based on the Slovin formula with an error rate of 5%. Data collection methods use observation, documentation and questionnaires. The data analysis method uses multiple regression analysis, hypothesis testing analysis, and percentage descriptive analysis using SPSS for Windows Release 20 program help</p>	<p>The results of the research show that the multiple regression analysis obtained the equation $Y = 30.773 + 0.435X_1 + 0.414X_2 + 0.2147X_3 + e$. Simultaneously, internship, learning achievement at school, and motivation to enter the world of work have a positive and significant effect on work readiness by 50.9%. Meanwhile, partially for industrial work practice (industrial work practice) it has a positive effect and significant to work readiness at 40.83%, learning achievement at school has an influence positive and significant for work readiness amounted to 2.75%, and motivation to enter the world of work had an influence positive and significant effect on work readiness of 2.72%.</p>
5	Desta Ambarsari dan Ati Sumiati	The Influence of Industrial Work Practice Achievement and Entrepreneurship Learning Outcomes on Entrepreneurial Interest of Class XII Accounting Class Students at	<p>This type of research is survey, with a quantitative approach. Data recording, interviews and questionnaire is a research technique. The sampling</p>	<p>The research results show that: there is a significant positive influence from industry entrepreneurial learning practices and achievements towards entrepreneurship Interest, Class XII Accounting at SMK</p>

	SMK Negeri 25 Jakarta	technique used is proportional random sampling. The population in this study was 77 students with a	Negeri 25 Jakarta. So if industry entrepreneurial learning practices and achievements increase, ie
		The sample consisted of 64 students of class XII accounting at SMK Negeri 25 Jakarta.	interest in entrepreneurship will also increase
6	Rusdarti Rusdarti dan Novia Ambarwat	The Influence of Industrial Work Practices (Prakerin), Work Motivation, Self-Efficacy on Students' Work Readiness	The population in this study were all class Data was collected using a questionnaire. Data analysis techniques use descriptive statistics, path analysis, and Sobel test.
			The results of this research show that there is an influence of work motivation on self-efficacy of (26.7%), there is an influence of work motivation on self-efficacy of (17%), there is an influence of self-efficacy on work readiness of (44.3%), there is The influence of internship through self-efficacy on work readiness is (13.99%) and there is an influence of work motivation through self-efficacy on job readiness of (8.99%). The conclusion of this research is that internship, work motivation and self-efficacy have an influence on work readiness of class XII students at SMK Negeri 1 Demak, as well as the self-efficacy variable can be an intervening variable.
7	Siti Wahyuni,Fad	The Influence of Industrial Work	This research was conducted using
			The results of the analysis and discussion

<p>jriah Hapsari, Mirna Herawati</p>	<p>Practices and Work Interests on Work Readiness in the Business and Industrial World of Vocational School Students</p>	<p>quantitative methods. The population was class The research instruments used were questionnaires and observation sheets. Data analysis techniques include multicollinearity test, heteroscedasticity, normality test, multiple linear regression, f test, t test, coefficient of determination and correlation coefficient.</p>	<p>show that Industrial Work Practices (X1) and Work Interest (X2) on Work Readiness (Y) have a strong influence, the correlation coefficient value is 0.750. Multiple linear regression analysis obtained the equation $Y = 4.779 + 0.512 X1 + 0.306 X2$. The F test obtained $F_{count} = 36.532$ so H_{a1} was accepted. Partially (t test) industrial work practices (X1) obtained $t_{count} = 4.447$ with a significance of $0.00 < 0.05$, so H_{a2} is accepted. Work Interest (X2) obtained $t_{count} = 3.318$ with a significance of $0.00 < 0.05$, so H_{a3} is accepted. Simultaneously (R²) industrial work practices and work interest have an effect on student work readiness, namely 54.6%</p>
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DISCUSSION

Lidya Dau, Munawar Thoharudin, Dessy Triana Relita (2019) show that there is a significant influence between industrial work practices on the work readiness of class industrial work practices and student accounting learning achievement simultaneously have a significant effect on work readiness at a significant level. Industrial work practice provides students with experience to develop skills according to their field of expertise which provides an overview of the world of work which can increase students' readiness to enter the world of work. Apart from that, industrial work practices are able to shape students' attitudes in adapting to new environments, such as adapting to the world of work and collaborating with other people to complete work. Industrial work practice provides practical experience for students to gain useful knowledge and work experience before going directly into the world of work.

Aulia Syalia (2017) shows the research results, namely: 1. There is an influence between industrial work practices and work motivation on the work readiness of class XII students at SMK Negeri 2 Tenggara 2. There is an influence between industrial work practices on the work readiness of class XII students at SMK Negeri 2 Tenggara. Likewise, research results from Rizal Eko Wibowo, Jarot Tri Bowo Santoso (2020) show that industrial work practices have a positive and significant effect on work readiness by 40.83%. The results of this research are supported by research results from Desta Ambarsari and Ati Sumiati (2016) shows the research results show that: there is a significant positive influence from industry practice and entrepreneurial learning achievement on entrepreneurial interest, Class XII Accounting at SMK Negeri 25 Jakarta. This research is in accordance with the opinion of Star et al. in Wena (2009) that vocational education is closely related to the world of work or industry, so practical learning and training plays a key role in equipping graduates to be able to adapt to the workforce. Winkel and Hastuti (2007) also stated that work readiness is also seen as an effort to strengthen a person's preparation in terms of the knowledge, skills, attitudes and values needed to pursue a job.

Rusdarti Rusdarti and Novia Ambarwati (2020) show that there is an influence of internship on self-efficacy of (26.7%), there is an influence of work motivation on self-efficacy of (17%), there is an influence of self-efficacy on work readiness of (44, 3%), there is an influence of internship through self-efficacy on work readiness of (13.99%) and there is an influence of work motivation through self-efficacy on job readiness of (8.99%). The conclusions of this research are internship, work motivation and self-efficacy influences the work readiness of class The effect on student work readiness is 54.6%. Quality human resources will support the sustainability of the country's economic development. Competent human resources also depend on the readiness condition of prospective workers, one of the supporting aspects includes the skills, knowledge and other understanding that have been learned. It can be interpreted that skills and knowledge experiences have a positive influence on work readiness, especially regarding the world of work. Human resource development can be carried out using a formal education and training approach (Dau, et al. 2019).

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that industrial work practices provide students with experience to develop skills according to their field of expertise. This was achieved because industrial practice can provide an overview of the world of work which can increase students' readiness to enter the world of work. Apart from that, students' work attitudes can also be more prepared because students are better able to adapt to new environments, such as adapting to the world of work and collaborating with other people to complete work. Industrial work practice is thus able to provide practical

experience for students to gain useful knowledge and work experience before going directly into the world of work.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Based on this research, further research can be continued with research which aims to determine the level of students' knowledge of the world of work. Furthermore, research can also be carried out using experimental methods to determine the effectiveness of providing knowledge about the world of work on students' work readiness.

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